

Store Brands Purchase Intentions: An Empirical Investigation of Super Markets in Al-Baha, Saudi Arabia

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Zia, Adil. “Store Brands Purchase Intentions: An Empirical Investigation of Super Markets in Al-Baha, Saudi Arabia.” *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 96–101.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451621>

Adil Zia

Corresponding Author, College of Business Administration, Albaha University, Albaha, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA)

Abstract

Buying of Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) products from organized retail stores involve many factors resulting in the final purchase decision and these factors influence perceived value and their buying behavior for deciding which type of product consumers would buy. Availability of store brands acts as an alternative to buy, and this trend is increasing day by day. Therefore, this study is to understand consumers purchase behavior for the store brand, which is an essential aspect for marketers and researchers. The Primary Data was collected, and SEM (Structured Equation Modeling) was employed to analyze data. The overall finding shows that consumer's perceived value contribute positively to their perceptions of store brands. Further, the results reveal that the Store Brand Perceived Quality leads to positive impressions which ultimately leads to the excellent possibility for them in repeat purchasing of store-brand products in the future. Thereby it was positively contributing to the development of store brand purchase intentions.

Keywords: store brand, consumer perceived value, buying behavior.

Introduction

Saudi consumers are very conscious consumers, and due to the cultural male and female segregation, they prefer to shop in a more spacious environment. Most of the time, it has been observed that Saudi consumers like modern looking stores with elegant and clean shopping environment. Saudi consumers pay more attention to price and consider it as one of the parameters for quality (Alfred, 2013). Around the world, all organized retail stores are striving towards developing stronger brands (Ailawadi & Keller, 2004; Anselmsson, Johansson, & Persson, 2007). The term Store brand is given to those products which are available in the store with the brand name of the stores (Ailawadi & Keller, 2004) Store image plays a vital role in the sale of store brands which also known as the private-labeled brands (Bao, Bao & Sheng, 2011). These store brands help retailers to create and manage store image, helps in gaining store loyalty and increased profit margins (Corstjens & Lal, 2000; Diallo, 2012; Sudhir & Talukdar, 2004). There are several incentives for retailers to create and manage store brands, such as increasing customer loyalty, profit margins, retailer performance, and a high-value offering in the

marketplace (Corstjens & Lal, 2000; Diallo, 2012; Sudhir & Talukdar, 2004). Zia & Khan (2018) found a positive relationship between the satisfactory store atmosphere and the buying behavior. Price plays a crucial role in the formation of store brands' composition (Richardson, Jain, & Dick, 1996). Store Brands are characterized by their low prices. Therefore store brands are considered to be convenient options for consumers (Ailawadi, Pauwels, & Steenkamp, 2008).

Literature Review

Based on various past studies following dimensions were found to determine Store Brand purchase intentions. These dimensions are Store commercial image, Store Social Price, Store Brand Image, Store Brand Perceived Quality, Store Brand Loyalty, and Store Brand Purchase Intentions.

Store Commercial Image

Store commercial image is different as the image of store in the minds of the customers; these images can be in the form of product quality, product assortment in the store, service, physical facilities layout, etc. (Anselmsson et al., 2007; Chowdhury, Reardon, & Srivastava, 1998).

Store Social Image

Accordingly, when consumers choose a store brand, they are influenced notably by the retailer's social reputation and image (Choi & Huddleston, 2013). More specifically, stores can be regarded as companies, whereby store image can be linked to aspects such as commitment and social interest, and global corporate strategy (Beristain & Zorrilla, 2011). In the present study, we find the social image of a store to receive from its social behavior and corporate background (Schmidt, 1995). Consequently, a store's social model has a positive impact on both the image and the purchase intention of its store-brand (Anselmsson et al., 2007; Beristain & Zorrilla, 2011).

Store Brand Price

Store brand associations or image Aaker (1991) defines brand associations – or image – as the information in the consumer's mind joined to the brand that creates positive attitudes towards the brand. According to Yoo, Donthu, and Lee (2000), brand associations consist of multiple images, instances, ideas, or facts that establish a robust network of brand knowledge, resulting in a higher purchase intention. Following Beristain and Zorrilla (2011), store brand associations are related to a specific type of consumer, as purchasing products or brands with an excellent value-for-money relationship lead to a smart buyer reaction, and store brands offer a more excellent price-quality relationship than manufacturer brands, thus leading to store brand support and purchase intention (Martos-Partial & González- Benito, 2011).

Store Brand Perceived Quality

According to Zeithaml (1988), perceived quality is conceptualized as consumers' global idea of a brand or product overall superiority or perfection. Perceived quality is also correlated to consumers' subjective perception of a commodity or brand attributes, and it constitutes a core brand value, as it is associated with the brand purchase and brand choice (Aaker, 1991). Following Bao et al. (2011), perceived quality is an intangible quality particular to a product category or a trademark name in the marketplace. Pappu, Quester, and Cooksey (2005) demonstrated that the more influential the quality consumers perceive in a trademark, the more likely they are to be loyal to it. Furthermore, the outcome of consumer's associations and perceived status can result in loyalty to a specific store brand (Choi & Huddleston, 2013).

Store Brand loyalty

According to Jacoby (1971), reliability should be studied as a behavior, with emphasis on the fact that allegiance also has an attitudinal component, present in the loyalty method. Moreover, Dick and Basu (1994) establish loyalty as the relationship between the relative attitude toward a brand, product, or service and patronage behavior. For this purpose, the present study evaluates both behavioral and attitudinal components of loyalty. Later, Oliver (1999) defines brand loyalty as a deeply held responsibility to rebuy or patronize a preferred product or service consistently in the future, despite situational influences, showing a powerful impact on purchase intention. According to Aaker (1991), brand loyalty indicates how likely a customer is to switch to another brand, especially when that brand changes, either in price or features. Myers (2003) remarked a significant positive relationship between the dimensions of store brand support, brand preference, and purchase plan. Following Diallo (2012), the purchase intention could be conceptualized as the consumer’s tendency to purchase a brand routinely and continue switching to other competing brands. In the present study, we refer to the purchase plan to operationalize the consumer purchase behavior toward store brands.

Hypothesis Related to Store Brand purchase intention

- H1: Store commercial image has a positive influence on store brand purchase intentions.
- H2: Store Social image has a positive influence on store brand purchase intentions.
- H3: Store Brand image has a positive influence on store brand purchase intentions.
- H4: Store Brand Purchase Quality has a positive influence on store brand purchase intentions.
- H5: Store Brand Loyalty has a positive influence on store brand purchase intentions.

Data collection

To test the hypotheses, a sample of primary data was collected through a structured online questionnaire and fieldwork in March to May 2019. The sample was collected randomly from a set of databases of higher education students and some public sector employees. Data consists of both male and female students, all of whom were consumers residing in Albaha province of Saudi Arabia.

Finally, a sample of 472 consumers were gathered, totaling 326 valid responses with a response rate of 69% approx. The last part of the questionnaire contained several socio-demographic questions. About the sample profile, 36.1% of the respondents were aged from 31 to 45, while 32.8% were aged 46 to 60. A total of 65.68% of the respondents were female. In terms of education level, over 38% of the participants had finished secondary education, while 17.5% had a higher education degree. Data also showed that all of the respondents were frequent store brand purchasers, as the majority stated purchasing store brands every week (44.7%) and 21.4% of the participants bought store brands every fifteen days.

Results and Discussions

Structural Equation Modeling was applied to find the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. In the given model, Store Commercial Image, Store Social Image, Store Brand Price, Store Brand Perceived Quality and Store Brand Loyalty are the independent factor, whereas Store Brand Purchase Intentions is the dependent variable.

The cumulative R-squared is 0.23, which is pity low. This means that even this model which is well accepted worldwide is only able to explain 23% store brand purchase intentions for the given sample. The needs to be further examined in future researches that how we can improve the measurement of Store Brand purchase intentions.

Figure 1: shows the regression weights on the arrows for each independent variable. The negative sign indicates the negative relationship between the Store Brand Prices and the Store Brand Perceived Intentions. Price of the store brand is the only factor which has an inverse relationship with purchase intentions. Therefore if rates are increased the store brand purchase intentions decreases and vice versa. Store brand perceived quality contributes to maximum, whereas Store Brand Loyalty contributes the lowest.

Figure1: Standardized Store Brand Purchase Intentions

In Table 1, it can be recognized that Store Brand Price and the Store Brand Perceived Quality are statistically significant. The p values for Store Brand Price and the Store Brand Perceived Quality are less than .001, and for the rest of the dimensions, it is more than that limit.

Table 1

Regression Weights			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Commercial_Image	.316	.155	2.032	.042	
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Social_Image	.230	.085	2.692	.007	
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Brand_Price	-.408	.067	-6.056	***	
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Brand_Perceived_Quality	.554	.098	5.630	***	
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Brand_Loyalty	.110	.215	.511	.609	

Table 2 shows the standardized regression weights. This indicated that store brand perceived quality has the 37.6 percent determines the store brand purchase intentions. This dimension has a positive significant impact on store brand purchase intention. On the other hand, Store Brand Price has a Negative considerable effect on the store brand purchase intentions. Highest predictors are the store brand perceived quality and store brand price.

Table 2

Standardized Regression Weights			Estimate	Hypothesis Findings
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Commercial_Image	.134	Supported
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Social_Image	.159	Supported
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Brand_Price	-.359	Supported
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Brand_Perceived_Quality	.376	Supported
Store_Brand_Purchase_Intention2	<---	Store_Brand_Loyalty	.031	Not Supported

Conclusion

It has been observed that Store commercial Image, Store Social Image, Store Brand Price, and Store Perceived Quality have a significant impact on the Store Brand Purchase Intention. Out of these four dimensions, Price has a negative meaningful relationship, and rest all have a positive significant relationship. Only one aspect has a positive insignificant relationship (Store Brand Loyalty). Table: 3 shows the level of importance of various factors for Store Brand Purchase intentions. It has been observed that Store Brand Perceived Quality (0.376) contribute maximum,

whereas Store Brand Loyalty (0.031) adds least for the Store Brand Purchase intentions. In future research, it is an area to explore why loyalty factor does not contribute to the store brand purchase intentions.

Table 3 Level of Impact

Independent factors	Regression Weights
Store Brand Perceived Quality	0.376
Store Brand Price	-0.359
Store Social Image	0.159
Store Commercial Image	0.134
Store Brand Loyalty	0.031

References

1. Alfred, O. (2013). Influences of price and quality on consumer purchase of mobile phone in The Kumasi Metropolis in Ghana a comparative study. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(1), 179-198.
2. Ailawadi, K. L., & Keller, K. L. (2004). Understanding retail branding: Conceptual insights and research priorities. *Journal of Retailing*, 80(4), 331–342. DOI:10.1016/j.jretai.2004.10.008
3. Anselmsson, J., Johansson, U., & Persson, N. (2007). The understanding price premium for grocery products: A conceptual model of customer-based brand equity. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 16(6), 401–414. DOI:10.1108/10610420710823762
4. Bao, Y., Bao, Y., & Sheng, S. (2011). Motivating purchase of private brands: Effects of store image, product signatures and, quality variation. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(2), 220–226. DOI:10.1016/j.jbusres.2010.02.007
5. Corstjens, M., & Lal, R. (2000). Building store loyalty through store brands. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 37(3), 281–291. DOI:10.1509/jmkr.37.3.281.18781
6. Diallo, M. F. (2012). Effects of store image and store brand price-image on store brand purchase intention: Application to an emerging market. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 19(3), 360–367. DOI:10.1016/j.jretconser.2012.03.010
7. Sudhir, K., & Talukdar, D. (2004). Does store brand patronage improve store patronage? *Review of Industrial Organization*, 24(2), 143–160. DOI:10.1023/b:reio.0000033353.52208.
8. Zia, A. & Khan, A. A. (2018). Measuring Service Quality of Apparel Stores using RSQS an Empirical Study of Albaha Region Saudi Arabia. *Research Review International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 3(12), 58–65. (UGC Approved ISSN:2455-3085) <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2110392>, Publons by Web of Science (WoS)
9. Ailawadi, K. L., Pauwels, K., & Steenkamp, J.-B. (2008). Private-label use and store loyalty. *Journal of Marketing*, 72(6), 19–30. DOI:10.1509/jmkg.72.6.19
10. Anselmsson, J., Johansson, U., & Persson, N. (2007). The understanding price premium for grocery products: A conceptual model of customer-based brand equity. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 16(6), 401–414. DOI:10.1108/10610420710823762
11. Chowdhury, J., Reardon, J., & Srivastava, R. (1998). Alternative modes of measuring store image: An empirical assessment of structured versus unstructured measures. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 6(2), 72–87.

Appendix 1. Variables and measurement scales

Constructs	Indicators
Store commercial image Chowdhury et al. (1998), Beristain and Zorrilla (2011)	Store X offers high quality products The store X offers services I'm looking for (ex. Pay over time, product return, etc.)
Store social image Handelman and Arnold (1999).	Store X has a long experience in retailing Store X makes efforts to introduce new products and services to the market
SB Price Aaker (1991), Netemeyer et al. (2004) (Modified on the Price parameter)	I associate products of store brand X with positive characteristics (ex. good prices) Customers of products of store brand X know how to buy and how much to buy. (purchasing with common sense)
SB perceived quality Doods et al. (1991)	The products of store brand X are high quality products The products of store brand X are reliable/trustworthy The products of store brand X give me the result I am looking for
SB loyalty Yoo et al. (2000)	I consider myself a consumer loyal to store brand X's products I will keep on buying store brand X.
SB purchase intention Netemeyer et al. (2004)	I would buy store brand X. I am likely to buy store brand X.